

SYNTHESIS OF O-CYANOALDEHYDES. PART I.

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None of the *o*-cyanoaldehydes have yet been synthesised, and in this paper we record our attempts to synthesise this important class of compounds which were required during the course of synthetical experiments in the group of alkaloids.

Attempts to convert *o*-aminobenzaldehydes into *o*-cyanoaldehydes by Sandmeyer's reaction under a large variety of different conditions were unsuccessful. The diazotisation of amines did not proceed smoothly and clear diazo solution was not obtained in any case under the usual conditions.

It was thought that the reaction might go better if the aldehyde group were first protected, but preliminary experiments to convert *o*-amino-Schiff's bases, oximes and acetals to the corresponding cyanoaldehydes were all unsuccessful. The chief difficulty lay in the diazotisation which could only be accomplished in strong acids. The scheme involving the use of the *o*-aminoaldoximes seemed to be particularly attractive as it was found that these amino-oximes could readily be prepared in almost quantitative yields from the corresponding nitro compounds (*vide* experimental part). The diazotisation of the *o*-aminoaldoximes could also be readily effected in strong hydrochloric acid solution, but the replacement of the diazo group by the cyano group could not be effected. Under one set of conditions azido-aldehydes were formed (*cf. Ber.*, 1901, **34**, 1331; 1927, **60**, 1741).

It was eventually found that the *o*-cyanoaldehydes could be obtained readily although only in poor yields (about 15%) by oxidation (with permanganate) of *o*-cyanocinnamic acids which could be synthesised readily in excellent yields from *o*-nitro-aldehydes and by other methods. *o*-Cyanobenzaldehyde (m.p. 76°) and 3-methoxy-6-cyanobenzaldehyde (m.p. 107°) were thus synthesised.

o-Aminocinnamic acids can be converted into the corresponding *o*-cyano-cinnamic acids in excellent yields. Oxidation of the *o*-cyanocinnamic acids by means of permanganate in presence of benzene takes a varied course, the main product in each case being a high melting sparingly soluble substance. Attempts are being made to improve the yield of *o*-cyanoaldehydes by the action of other oxidising agents like ozone, nitrogen peroxide on *o*-cyanocinnamic acids.

Synthesis of other methoxy-*o*-cyanoaldehydes and dimethoxy-*o*-cyanoaldehydes is reserved for a future communication.

EXPERIMENTAL.

2-Amino-3-methoxybenzaloxime.—*m*-Hydroxybenzaldehyde was methylated by means of dimethyl sulphate in alkaline solution in an yield of about 90% (Chakravarti, Vaidyanathan and Venkatasubban, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 574) and then nitrated under conditions similar to those used by Ayling, Hinkel and Morgan (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 1115). 2-Nitro-3-methoxybenzaldehyde which was thus formed in about 95% yield was purified by repeated crystallisations from benzene and was converted into its oxime in the following manner: The aldehyde (1.6 g.) was dissolved in the least amount of alcohol and treated with a solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1.03 g.) and sodium hydroxide (1.2 g.) in water and the whole allowed to remain for 24 hours. On acidifying the oxime was precipitated in quantitative yield. It was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 170°.

The oxime (10 g.) was dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution (5 g. in 50 c.c. of water) and added to freshly precipitated ferrous hydroxide from ferrous sulphate (85.5 g. in 50 c.c. of water) and sodium hydroxide (26.3 g. in water). The reduction was carried out in the cold in alkaline medium. The whole was well stirred, filtered and the precipitate washed several times with cold water. The filtrate (along with the washings) was then saturated with carbon dioxide when the amine-oxime was precipitated in an yield of over 80%. On recrystallisation from methyl alcohol it melted at 136-37°. (Found: N, 17.0. $C_8H_{10}O_2N_2$ requires N, 16.9 per cent).

6-Amino-2 : 3-dimethoxybenzaloxime.—6-Nitro-2 : 3-dimethoxybenzaldehyde was prepared from *o*-vanillin by the method previously described (Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 215) and converted into the oxime thus:—The aldehyde (2.1 g.) was dissolved in alcohol and treated with a solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1 g.) and sodium hydroxide (1.2 g.) in water. The mixture was allowed to stand for 24 hours and then just acidified with acetic acid when the oxime was precipi-

tated in quantitative yield. The oxime crystallises in needles from alcohol, m.p. 137°. (Found : N, 12.6. $C_9H_{10}O_5N_2$ requires N, 12.4 per cent).

The oxime (4.6 g.) was dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution (2 g. in 20 c.c. of water) and the solution added to the precipitate obtained from crystallised ferrous sulphate (33.8 g.) and sodium hydroxide (10.5 g. in 200 c.c. of water). The whole was vigorously shaken for about 1/4 hour and then the ferric hydroxide filtered, washed several times with cold water. The filtrate and washings were saturated with carbon dioxide when the amino-oxime was precipitated in an excellent yield. It crystallises from methyl alcohol in shining plates, m.p. 147°. (Found : N, 14.5. $C_9H_{12}O_3N_2$ requires N, 14.3 per cent).

Diazotisation and replacement of the diazo group by the cyano group of 2-amino-3-methoxybenzaloxime and 6-amino-2 : 3-dimethoxybenzaloxime were tried under the following conditions :—

- (i) Diazotisation and replacement of the diazo groups under the usual conditions.
- (ii) Diazotisation in presence of excess of concentrated hydrochloric acid at -5°, neutralisation of the free acid by sodium hydroxide, barium hydroxide or sodium carbonate solution and subsequent treatment with cuprous cyanide under the usual conditions.
- (iii) Diazotisation of the amines in presence of excess of strong mineral acid, the diazo solution and alkali being added at the same time to the cuprous cyanide, keeping the cyanide solution just alkaline throughout the reaction.

Although diazotisation did seem to proceed in (ii) and (iii), cyano compounds could not be obtained under any of the conditions. Under conditions (ii) and (iii) 2-azido-aldehydes were formed and these are being further investigated.

6-Amino-3-methoxycinnamic Acid.—*m*-Hydroxybenzaldehyde was nitrated and 6-nitro-3-hydroxybenzaldehyde separated by the method of Friedlander and Schenck (*Ber.*, 1914, 47, 3046). 6-Nitro-3-hydroxybenzaldehyde was methylated by means of dimethyl sulphate in alkaline solution and the methoxy compound converted into 6-nitro-3-methoxycinnamic acid (m.p. 227°) in almost quantitative yield by malonic acid-pyridine method. A solution of 6-nitro-3-methoxycinnamic acid (11.6 g.) in dilute ammonia was added to a solution of ferrous sulphate (106 g. in 150 c.c. of water). To the mixture heated on the steam-bath was then gradually added concentrated ammonia (42 c.c.) while the contents were vigorously shaken throughout. After all the ammonia had been added, the whole was further heated for 1/4 hour, filtered, the filtrate concentrated down to

one third its volume and then carefully made just acid. The amino-acid was precipitated as a crystalline yellow powder, m.p. 186° , yield 70%. The hydrochloride crystallised from water in prismatic needles, m.p. 204° (decomp.). (Found : C, 52.1; H, 5.3. $C_{10}H_{12}O_3NCl$ requires C, 52.3; H, 5.2 per cent).

6-Cyano-3-methoxycinnamic Acid.—A mixture of 6-amino-3-methoxycinnamic acid (7 g.), water (45 c.c.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (10 g.) was cooled to 0° and diazotised with a solution of sodium nitrite (3.4 g.). The clear diazo solution was added to a hot solution of potassium cuprous cyanide, obtained by adding a solution of potassium cyanide (12.6 g. in 22 c.c. of water) to a solution of copper sulphate (11 g. in 67 c.c. of water). The whole was heated on the water-bath for one hour, cooled and acidified. The precipitated cyano-acid was filtered, washed and dissolved in dilute sodium carbonate solution. The sodium carbonate solution was acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The precipitated cyano-acid was filtered, washed and recrystallised from methyl alcohol (charcoal) in long clusters of needles, m.p. 220° . (Found : C, 64.8; H, 4.2. $C_{11}H_9O_3N$ requires C, 65.0; H, 4.4 per cent).

6-Cyano-3-methoxybenzaldehyde.—A solution of 6-cyano-3-methoxycinnamic acid (2.5 g.) in sodium carbonate solution was covered with benzene (300 c.c.) in a separating funnel and a cold saturated solution of potassium permanganate (4.2 g.) was gradually added with vigorous shaking. After all the permanganate had been added the mixture was further shaken for 15 minutes, filtered and the precipitate washed several times with small quantities of benzene. The benzene layer was separated from the aqueous layer of the filtrate, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. It was then concentrated to about 30 c.c. when a crystalline substance (A) (0.65 g.) separated, which on repeated crystallisation from benzene was obtained as prismatic needles, m.p. 218° . The mother liquors from (A) on further concentration deposited first more of the substance (A) and then 6-cyano-3-methoxybenzaldehyde, which was readily separated, the aldehyde being much more soluble in benzene. The latter on repeated crystallisation from alcohol was obtained in clusters of needles, m.p. 107° . (Found : C, 67.2; H, 4.3. $C_9H_7O_2N$ requires C, 67.1; H, 4.4 per cent).

The substance (A) could not be readily hydrolysed.

From the aqueous layer of the filtrate on concentration and acidification a mixture of the starting acid and a new acid (m.p. about 132°) was precipitated.

o-Cyanocinnamic acid was prepared from *o*-nitroso- β -naphthol by Beckmann's transformation (Edward, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 815).

o-Cyanobenzaldehyde.—*o*-Cyanocinnamic acid was oxidised under

conditions similar to those described above for 6-cyano-3-methoxycinnamic acid. From the benzene layer at first a sparingly soluble substance crystallising in needles, m.p. 227°, separated and then *o*-cyanobenzaldehyde, which on repeated crystallisation melted at 76°. (Found: C, 73.0; H, 3.7. C_8H_5ON requires C, 73.3; H, 3.8 per cent). From the aqueous layer, the starting acid, *o*-cyanobenzoic acid and an acid (m.p. 197-202°) were isolated.

2-Amino-3-methoxycinnamic Acid.—12 G. of 2-nitro-3-methoxycinnamic acid (which was synthesised from 2-nitro-3-methoxybenzaldehyde by the malonic acid-pyridine method) dissolved in dilute ammonia were added to a solution of ferrous sulphate (106 g. in 150 c.c. of water) which had been heated on the water-bath to about 90°. Ammonia (45 c.c.) was then added gradually with vigorous shaking and after all the addition, heating and shaking were continued for further 15 minutes. The whole was then filtered, precipitated, washed several times with dilute ammonia and the filtrate and washings concentrated to one fourth of its bulk and then made just acid when 2-amino-3-methoxycinnamic acid was precipitated, yield 50%. It crystallised from water in yellow glittering prisms, m.p. 189° (decomp.). (Found: C, 62.2; H, 6.0. $C_{10}H_{11}O_3 N$ requires C, 62.2; H, 5.7 per cent).

2-Cyano-3-methoxycinnamic Acid.—A mixture of 2-amino-3-methoxycinnamic acid (3.5 g.), water (23 c.c.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (5 c.c.) was cooled to 0° and diazotised with a solution of sodium nitrite (1.7 g.). The clear diazo solution was added to a hot solution of potassium cuprous cyanide obtained by adding to a solution of copper sulphate (5.5 g. in 34 c.c. of water) a solution of potassium cyanide (6.3 g. in 11 c.c. of water). The whole was heated on the water-bath for 1 hour, cooled and acidified when crude cyano-acid was precipitated which was filtered, washed and then dissolved in dilute sodium carbonate solution and acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The precipitated cyano-acid was filtered, washed and crystallised from alcohol or acetone (charcoal). It crystallised in needles, m.p. 149°. (Found: C, 64.7; H, 4.3. $C_{11}H_9O_3 N$ requires C, 65.0; H, 4.4 per cent).

Yields in this series are lower than in the corresponding 6-cyano series due probably to increased steric difficulty, both the *ortho* positions to the nitro or amino group being occupied.

Experiments on the oxidation of 2-cyano-3-methoxycinnamic acid are in progress.